

Complexes of Biguanide and Malonic-Diamidine

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THE unusual colour change and precipitate which can be produced by adding biguanide (I) to solutions of copper salts has been already observed by the discoverer of the base about hundred years ago¹. However, the potential of biguanide as a chelating agent and an useful analytical reagent was brought to light mainly by Priyadarajan Rây². By synthesising a large number of substituted biguanides and studying their behaviour as ligands with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Pd(II) as well as Co(III), Cr(III) and even Ag(III), Rây reached the conclusion that the various metal cations were coordinating to one of the two primary amino groups of (I) (nitrogens 1 or 5) as well as the nitrogen of an imino group (4 or 2) and that a tautomeric change took place simultaneously i. e. a proton transfer from the nitrogen of the coordinating imino group to the non-coordinating amino group as formulated in structure II³.

Recently, however, the structure of bis-(biguanido)-nickel(II) chloride has been elucidated by X-ray crystallographic techniques⁴, revealing that the complex is a planar molecule of high symmetry. When the result (figure 1) is compared with structure II it is seen that the formation of 6-membered chelate rings was correctly predicted by Professor Rây and that the differences concern the phenomena of tautomerism and mesomerism

Figure 1 : Square planar complexes of biguanide. Distances (\AA units) and angles given are those of the Ni(II) complex. The M-N distance of the Cu(II) complex is somewhat longer.

only. Proton transfers from one nitrogen to another within the ligand molecule are extremely facile which makes it impossible to locate the hydrogens by chemical methods, but the ¹H nmr spectrum of anhydrous biguanide complexes reveals that the 14 protons of the complex are present in sets of 2 (positions 3), 4 (positions 2 and 4) and 8 (positions 1 and 5) as is the case in the free ligand of formula I. The bond distances and bond angles show that all the C-N bonds within the complex have appreciable double bond character, those within the chelate ring somewhat more than the bonds to the non-coordinated nitrogens 1 and 5. The charge of the complex cation resides therefore to a large extent on the nitrogens, but is not located as suggested by formula II.

The two nitrogens in position 3 clearly have the biggest share of the positive charge and the protons bonded to them must be the most acidic ones. Indeed, these protons of the central imino groups are lost in alkaline solution (pH around 12) and the free, sparingly soluble uncharged complex base is precipitated. The protons bonded to the nitrogens in position 3 can also be replaced by silver and mercury⁵. It is of interest that the special behaviour of the imino groups was recognised very early and has given rise to complex formulations showing the metal directly bonded to the nitrogens in position 3 by "primary valencies"⁶. Werner's "primary valencies"⁷ however are best interpreted today as a stoichiometric bearing; indeed the hydrogens of the imino groups have been replaced formally by the metal in the uncharged deprotonated biguanide complex $[M(C_2H_5N_5)_2]$.

The importance of the nitrogens in position 3 for the stability of the biguanide complexes is most strikingly demonstrated chemically by replacing them with carbon. The novel ligand thus obtained is malonic-diamidine III. It is easily obtained from the dinitrile IV which is first converted to the malonic-diiminoether V and the latter reacted with ammonia in alcoholic solution⁷, yielding the di-cation VI.

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The complexes of malonic-diamidine must be prepared from alcoholic solutions to prevent hydrolysis. The dihydrochloride VI is suspended in ethanol, dissolved with a small quantity of concentrated ammonia and the stoichiometric amount (0.5 mol) of the metal, nickel or copper, added in the form of its ammine complex in ammoniacal solution. The crystallized complex chlorides have been obtained.

Bis-(malonic-diamidine)-nickel Chloride :

found : C, 21.78 ; H, 4.92 ; N, 33.71 ; Cl, 21.35%
calcd. for

$\text{NiC}_6\text{H}_8\text{N}_8\text{Cl}_2$: C, 21.85; H, 4.89; N, 33.97; Cl, 21.50%

Bis-(malonic-diamidine)-copper(II) Chloride :

found : C, 21.55 ; H, 4.85 ; N, 33.42 ; Cl, 21.0 %
calcd. for $\text{CuC}_6\text{H}_8\text{N}_8\text{Cl}_2$:

C, 21.53 ; H, 4.82 ; N, 33.49 ; Cl, 21.19 %

The complexes of III are strikingly similar to those of I with respect to their colours, but very dissimilar with respect to stability. The red copper salt $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{N}_4)_2]\text{Cl}_2$ dissolves easily in water to a purple solution, the colour of which changes continuously on standing, producing finally a green precipitate. The aqueous solutions of the deep yellow nickel salt $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{N}_4)_2]\text{Cl}_2$ are only slightly more stable. Addition of acid or alkali destroys both complexes immediately and irreversibly, the latter precipitating the metal hydroxides. In contrast to the biguanide complexes, the malonic-diamidine complexes cannot be deprotonated, decomposition occurring even when the base: ethoxide is added to anhydrous alcoholic solutions of the complexes.

The structure of the malonic-diamidine complexes, as revealed by X-ray diffraction is presented by figure 2. Again are the nitrogens 2 and 4 bonded to the metal forming an almost perfect square.

Figure 2 : Square planar complexes of malonic-diamidine. Distances and angles given are those of the Cu(II) complex. The M-N distance of the Ni(II) complex is somewhat shorter (1.87 Å).

However, the cationic complex molecule is no longer planar, one of the carbons connecting the amidine groups being above and the other below the plane of the coordination square. The hydrogens of the CH_2

group complete an only slightly distorted tetrahedron of the connecting carbon which replaces the nitrogen in position 3 of biguanide. The C-C connections are clearly single bonds of the normal length without any appreciable double bond character. Whereas the distances M-N and N-C of the chelate rings and the angles N-M-N and M-N-C are almost the same in the biguanide- and malonic-diamidine complexes, is the C-C bond in the latter appreciably longer (1.51 Å) than the C-N (3) bond in the former (1.32 Å), which thus pushes the connecting CH_2 out of the plane formed by the two coordinated nitrogens and the two amidine

carbons. The fragment $\text{M}-\text{NH}-\text{C} \begin{matrix} \nearrow \text{NH}_2 \\ \searrow \text{C} \end{matrix}$ is planar, including the hydrogens, but these planes of the two moieties of the ligand molecule are inclined to each other and also to the plane of the coordination square.

The two amidine groups in malonic-diamidine and its complexes are electronically independent from one another because of the separating CH_2 . Only the C-N connections have double bond character. Whereas their bond order is exactly 1.5 in the dichloride VI, the bond to the coordinated NH has somewhat more than half the share of the double bond, and the C-NH₂ somewhat less in the complexes. The fact, that the two amidine groups share no electrons and do not act in unison is no doubt the reason for the decreased stability of the malonic-diamidine complexes in comparison to the biguanide complexes. The latter are therefore stabilized by resonance energy to an appreciable extent.

The non-planarity of the malonic-diamidine complexes⁸ is pictured once more in figure 3. It is obvious that these cations cannot be so closely packed as the planar cations of the biguanide complexes which probably causes the increased solubility of the former.

Figure 3 : The structure of the cation $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{N}_4)_2]^{2+}$

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